

NONLINEAR CONSTANT LIFE MODEL FOR FATIGUE LIFE PREDICTION OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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1 Introduction

Composite materials are widely used to aircraft and spacecraft due to its light-weight, yet excellent mechanical properties compared to metal by using its directional characteristics. Many studies have been done for fatigue failure of composite material because fatigue is one of the main causes of failure. For estimating the fatigue life, the critical points are the S-N type selection, statistical interpretation of fatigue data, selection of the appropriate constant life diagram formulation, fatigue failure criterion, and the damage summation rule [1,2]. Among these critical points, we focused on the effect of CLD formulation on life prediction.

The classic linear Goodman diagram[3] is the most widely used CLD, because of its simplicity. But it is not suitable for composite materials because of its damage mechanisms under tension and compression is different. Therefore straight lines connecting the UTS and UCS with points of the $R = -1$ line for different numbers of cycles are not capable to describe the fatigue behavior of composite materials. Several different models have been presented in the literature to properly describe characteristics of composite materials. Starting from the basic idea of Goodman diagram and the nonlinear Gerber equation, different modifications were proposed. Based on the linear interpolation between different S-N curves in a modified Goodman diagram concept[4-6], analytical expressions of any desired S-N curve so called piecewise linear CLD is developed by Philippidis et al [2]. Comparison of CLDs by predicting ability of new S-N curve shows that piecewise linear CLD is the most accurate of the compared formulations when more than three S-N curves available. More accurate estimation of fatigue

life is possible with increasing number of S-N curves. But it cannot properly describe for fatigue behavior with varying R -ratio when fewer S-N curves available due to its linear characteristics. Kawai[7,8] proposed a nonlinear CLD that can be derived by using only one "critical" S-N curve. The critical R -ratio is equal to the ratio of the UCS over UTS of the examined material. The main drawback of this model is the need for experimental data for this specific S-N curve. Therefore, it cannot be applied to existing fatigue databases. However, the minimum amount of data required is an advantage of the methodology. In this study, a nonlinear constant life diagram formulation is proposed and the influence of the constant life diagram formulation on the prediction of the fatigue life was examined. The proposed model needs three or more S-N curves and requires nonlinear regression process. With a small number of available S-N curves, proposed CLD model can describe fatigue behavior more properly with varying R -ratio compared to piecewise linear model which is currently the most accurate CLD. The most commonly used CLD formulations are evaluated according to its accuracy of estimation for unknown S-N curves. Based on the results, recommendations concerning the applicability, advantages and disadvantages of each of the examined CLD formulations are discussed.

2 Theories of CLD model

Constant life diagram was created to consider the effect of the mean stress and material anisotropy on the fatigue life of the composite material. CLD acts as a master diagram and represents constant fatigue life behavior for entire range of loading type (comp-

ression-compression, tension-compression, and tension-tension loading). CLD makes it possible to estimate S-N curve for specific loading patterns for which no experimental data exist. The main parameters of CLD are the mean stress, σ_m , the alternating stress, σ_a , and the R -ratio, which defined as the minimum stress over the maximum stress.

2.1 Linear CLD

The linear CLD model is based on a single S-N curve that should be experimentally derived under fully reversed loading ($R = -1$). Constant life lines are created by connecting constant life data points and static strength. Unknown S-N curves are simply calculated by linear interpolation. This CLD model constitutes a modification of the Goodman line[3]. The general formulae of the model are:

$$\sigma_a = \sigma_{a0}(1 - (\sigma_m / UTS)), \text{ For } \sigma_m > 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\sigma_a = \sigma_{a0}(1 - (\sigma_m / UCS)), \text{ For } \sigma_m < 0 \quad (2)$$

where, σ_{a0} is the cyclic stress amplitude for a given constant value of life N under fatigue loading.

2.2 Piecewise linear CLD [2]

The piecewise linear CLD is derived by linear interpolation between known S-N curves in the $(\sigma_m - \sigma_a)$ plane. A limited number of experimentally determined S-N curves along with the ultimate tensile and compressive stresses of the materials are required for this CLD model. Typically, S-N curves representing the entire range of possible loading are used for piecewise linear CLDs, normally at $R = 0.1$ for tension-tension loading, $R = -1$ for tension-compression loading, and $R = 10$ for compression-compression loading patterns. Constant life lines are constructed by connecting the same fatigue life cycle data points on each of the S-N curves. By linear interpolation between known values of fatigue and strength data, unknown S-N curves are estimated. Following analytical expressions for the description of each region of the piecewise linear CLD were developed in [2].

1. If R' is in the T-T sector of the CLD, and between UTS and the first known R -ratio in the tension region, R_{1TT} ,

$$\sigma'_a = \frac{UTS}{\frac{UTS}{\sigma_{a,1TT}} + r' - r_{1TT}} \quad (3)$$

where, σ'_a and $\sigma'_{a,1TT}$ are the stress amplitudes corresponding to R' and R_{1TT} , respectively and $r_i = (1 + R_i) / (1 - R_i)$, and $r' = (1 + R') / (1 - R')$.

2. If R is located between any of two known R -ratios, R_i and R_{i+1} ,

$$\sigma'_a = \frac{\sigma_{a,i}(r' - r_{i+1})}{(r_i - r')\frac{\sigma_{a,i}}{\sigma_{a,i+1}} + (r' - r_{i+1})} \quad (4)$$

3. If R' is in the C-C region of the CLD, and between UCS and first known R -ratio in the compression region, R_{1CC} ,

$$\sigma'_a = \frac{UCS}{\frac{UCS}{\sigma_{a,1CC}} + r' - r_{1CC}} \quad (5)$$

where, σ'_a and $\sigma'_{a,1CC}$ are the stress amplitudes corresponding to R' and R_{1CC} , respectively.

2.3 Kawai's CLD [7,8]

Kawai and his coworkers developed an asymmetric constant life diagram, designated the anisomorphic constant fatigue life (CFL) diagram in [7]. Main feature of this formulation is that it can be constructed by using only one experimentally derived S-N curve, which is called critical S-N curve. The R -ratio of this S-N curve is defined as the ratio of the UCS over UTS of the material. The formulation is based on three main assumptions: 1. The stress amplitude for a given constant value of fatigue life is greatest at the critical stress ratio. 2. The shape of the CFL curves changes progressively from a straight line to a parabola with increasing fatigue life. 3. The diagram is bounded by the static failure envelope that consists of two straight lines connecting the peak point on the critical straight line with the UTS and UCS, respectively. The CFL formulation depends on the position of the mean stress, σ_m , in the domain $[\sigma_C, \sigma_T]$ as follows.

$$\frac{\sigma_a - \sigma_a^\chi}{\sigma_a^\chi} = \begin{cases} \left(\frac{\sigma_m - \sigma_m^\chi}{UTS - \sigma_m^\chi} \right)^{(2-\psi_\chi)}, & UTS \geq \sigma_m \geq \sigma_m^\chi \\ \left(\frac{\sigma_m - \sigma_m^\chi}{UCS - \sigma_m^\chi} \right)^{(2-\psi_\chi)}, & UCS \leq \sigma_m \leq \sigma_m^\chi \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

where, σ_a^χ and σ_m^χ represent the alternating and mean stress components of the fatigue stress for a given constant value of life N under fatigue loading at the critical stress ratio, $\chi = UCS / UTS$. The

variable ψ_x denotes the fatigue strength ratio and it is defined as

$$\psi_x = \frac{\sigma_{\max}^x}{\sigma_B} \quad (7)$$

where, σ_B (>0) is the reference strength to define the peak of the static failure envelope in the $(\sigma_m - \sigma_a)$ plane.

2.4 Taeyoung's CLD model

In this study, nonlinear constant life model was developed to describe fatigue behavior of composite materials. Plotting constant life data in $(\sigma_m - \sigma_a)$ plane using S-N curves for different R -ratio shows constant life data varies with fatigue life cycles as well as load type (i.e. compression or tensile load). Constant life line changes its shape depending on fatigue life cycles, N . It usually shows parabolic form (concave or convex) or linear form. In proposed CLD, nonlinearity is reflected yet it has simple equation and calculations. This formulation depends on the position of the mean stress and fatigue strength under fully reversed loading at given value of fatigue life. Following simple expressions are representing the proposed constant life diagram model:

$$\sigma_a = \sigma_{a0} \left(1 - \left(\frac{\sigma_m}{UTS} \right)^{\alpha_T} \right), \quad \text{For } \sigma_m > 0 \quad (8)$$

$$\sigma_a = \sigma_{a0} \left(1 - \left(\frac{\sigma_m}{UCS} \right)^{\alpha_C} \right), \quad \text{For } \sigma_m < 0 \quad (9)$$

where, σ_{a0} is the cyclic stress amplitude for a given constant value of life, N , under fully reversed loading. The tensile and compressive fitting parameter, α_T and α_C , is calculated by nonlinear regression. This variable reflects the trend of the constant life data position.

3 Experimental data

The predicting accuracy of all the examined CLD formulations was assessed on two constant amplitude data sets retrieved from the databases. Fatigue data from tests under various stress ratio including tension-tension, tension-compression, and compression-compression loading can be found in these databases.

3.1 Material #1

GFRP multidirectional specimens cut at 45° off-axis from a laminate with a stacking sequence of $[0/(\pm 45)_2/0]_T$, [6]. The constant amplitude fatigue test results are considered as the first example for comparison of the CLD formulations. The selected test set is consisted of 57 valid fatigue data points which are distributed in four S-N curves, at stress ratios of 0.5, 0.1, -1 and 10. The maximum cyclic stress level ranged between 45 and 130 MPa, and loading cycles at failure between 1420 and 3.46 million. Tests were conducted at a frequency of 10 Hz. Details of the material and testing procedures can be found in [5]. The UTS for this material was determined as 139 MPa, and the UCS was 106 MPa.

Fig. 1. Dependence of the fitting parameter, α , on life for material #1.

Fig. 2. Dependence of the fitting parameter, α , on life for material #2.

3.2 Material #2

The second material is GFRP multidirectional specimens with a stacking sequence of $[90/0/\pm 45/0]_s$, based on experimental fatigue data from the DOE/MSU database[9]. In the DOE/MSU database the material has the code name DD16. The material was tested under constant amplitude for 12 R -ratios(0.9, 0.8, 0.7, 0.5, 0.1, -0.5, -1, -2, 10, 2, 1.43, and 1.1). For comparison of CLD formulations, experimental data were collected under six R -ratios (0.8, 0.5, 0.1, -0.5, -1, 10). The maximum stress level was between 85 and 500 MPa, and loading cycles at failure ranged from 27 cycles to 30.4 million. Details of the material and test conditions can be found in [9]. The UTS for this material was determined as 632 MPa, and the UCS was 402 MPa.

4 Results

Three of four(material #1), and four of six(material #2) existing S-N curves and the static strength

values were used as input data. The static strength ratio for the Kawai CLD are -0.76, and -0.63, but no S-N curve under this R -ratio is available. So S-N curve at $R = -1$ was used for the construction of the linear and the Kawai CLD. Fig.1. and Fig.2. show change in fitting parameter for each material. With increasing fatigue life cycles, compressive fitting parameter, α_c , shows significant changes, while tensile parameter, α_t , slightly changing.

4.1 Material #1

CLDs based on the different formulations presented in Fig.3. Linear and Kawai CLDs are inaccurate for the examined material, while the prediction of the piecewise linear diagram for the S-N data at $R = 0.5$ is accurate($R^2 = 0.85$). For Kawai's model, absence of critical S-N data might be the reason for the inaccurate result. S-N data prediction for the material #1 by Proposed CLD model was shown the most accurate result($R^2 = 0.90$). Fig.4. shows predicted S-N curves of different CLD formulations.

Fig.3. Constant life diagrams for material #1 (A-linear, B-piecewise linear, C-Kawai, D-Taeyoung).

4.2 Material #2

Constant life diagrams according to the described models are presented in Fig.5. The linear CLD is accurate only for the prediction of the curve at the stress ratio, $R = -0.5$ ($R^2 = 0.86$) but failed to accurately predict the curve at $R = 0.8$. Kawai's model failed to accurately predict the curve for both S-N data at $R = -0.5$ and $R = 0.8$. Inappropriate assumption of critical S-N data might be the reason for the inaccurate result. The piecewise linear CLD predicted

Table.1. Predicting ability of the CLD formulations in terms of the coefficient of determination (R^2).

	Mat. #1	Mat. #2	
	R=0.5	R=-0.5	R=0.8
Linear	0.50	0.86	0.51
Pw. linear	0.85	0.91	0.83
Kawai	0.50	0.78	0.49
Proposed	0.90	0.83	0.74

best result in both cases. The predictions of proposed CLD model is slightly lower accuracy than that of piecewise CLD. Fig.5. and 6. show predicted S-N curve of CLD formulations. For $R = -0.5$, it is observed that proposed model predicted conservative S-N curve.

Fig.4. Predicted S-N curves for material #1 ($R=0.5$).

Fig.5. Constant life diagrams for material #2 (A-linear, B-piecewise linear, C-Kawai, D- Taeyoung).

5 Conclusions

Nonlinear constant life model was developed and proposed to describe fatigue behavior of composite materials. And a comparison of the commonly used and proposed models for derivation of constant life diagrams for composite materials was carried out in this paper. Four methods were described and their prediction accuracy was evaluated over constant amplitude fatigue data of GFRP materials. As shown in result, inappropriate choice of constant life diagram can produce very optimistic or very conservative S-N curves, which could overestimate or underestimate life. Thus, the selection of an accurate CLD formulation is essential for the accuracy of a fatigue life prediction. The simplicity is offered by Linear and Kawai's model. These models need minimum data sets, but for Kawai's model, additional experiment of critical S-N is inevitable because most of the databases do not have critical experiment data. In this paper, the absence of critical S-N data might be the reason for the inaccurate result. The piecewise linear model predicted relatively accurate S-N data. But piecewise linear model cannot describe nonlinearity of fatigue behavior. The proposed nonlinear CLD model is relatively simple with simple equations and nonlinear regression. The proposed model predicted relatively accurate S-N curves and well described nonlinearity of fatigue life distribution. For more realistic description of the fatigue behavior of composite material additional research will be performed to improve the accuracy of this model.

Fig.6. Predicted S-N curves for material #2 (R=-0.5).

References

- [1] I. P. Bond "Fatigue life prediction for GRP subjected to variable amplitude fatigue". *Composites: Part A*, Vol. 30, pp 961-970, 1999.
- [2] T. P. Philippidis and A. P. Vassilopoulos "Life prediction methodology for GFRP laminates under spectrum loading". *Composites: Part A*, Vol. 35, pp 657-666, 2004.
- [3] J. Goodman "*Mechanics applied to engineering*". Longman, Green & company, London, 1899.
- [4] J. F. Mandell, D. D. Samborsky, L. Wang and N. K. Wahl "New fatigue data for wind turbine blade materials". *Journal of Solar Energy Engineering*, Vol. 125, pp 506-514, 2003.
- [5] H. J. Sutherland and J. F. Mandell "Optimized constant life diagram for the analysis of fiberglass composites used in wind turbine blades". *Journal of Solar Energy Engineering*, Vol. 127, pp 563-569, 2005.
- [6] T. P. Philippidis and A. P. Vassilopoulos "Complex stress state effect on fatigue life of GRP laminates. Part I, experimental". *International Journal of Fatigue*, Vol. 24, pp 813-823, 2002.
- [7] M. Kawai and M. Koizumi "Nonlinear constant fatigue life diagrams for carbon/epoxy laminates at room temperature". *Composites: Part A*, Vol. 38, pp 2342-2353, 2007.
- [8] M. Kawai "A method for identifying asymmetric dissimilar constant fatigue life diagrams for CFRP laminates". *Key engineering materials*, Vol. 334-335, pp 61-64, 2007.
- [9] J. F. Mandell and D. D. Samborsky "*DOE/MSU composite material fatigue database*". Sandia National Laboratories, SAND97-3002, 2010.

Fig.7. Predicted S-N curves for material #2 (R=0.8).